

Horizon Europe Project PLANET4B

COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION STRATEGY (VERSION 1.0)

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

PLANET4B

Funded by
the European Union

PLANET4B receives funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101082212.

UK Research
and Innovation

This project is funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee.

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Views and opinions are of those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, European Commission, the government of the United Kingdom, or the government of Switzerland. The European Union, the European Commission, the government of the United Kingdom, or the government of Switzerland cannot be held responsible for them.

PLANET4B

BETTER DECISIONS FOR BIODIVERSITY AND PEOPLE

Key deliverable information

Project acronym	PLANET4B
Project title	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social Learning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
Starting date	01 st November 2022
Duration	36 months
Website	https://planet4b.eu/
Project coordination and scientific lead team	Ilkhom Soliev; Alex Franklin; Agnes Zolyomi; Torsten Wähler

Deliverable number	D5.1
Deliverable title	Communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy (version 1.0)
Task leader	Good Issue Ltd. (GD)
Corresponding author	Gyula Gábor Tóth
Dissemination level	Public
Status	Final

Deliverable description

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) plan on communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities of the consortium with key messages, main dissemination actors, main channels, specific activities, timeline, KPIs, verification of KPIs and monitoring.

Version	Status	Date	Authors/Reviewers
0.1	Draft	19/04/2023	Authors: Gyula Gábor Tóth (GD); Zsuzsanna Király (GD); Mária Csikai (GD)
0.2	Draft	21/04/2023	Reviewers: Alex Franklin (CU); Torsten Wähler (MLU); Agnes Zolyomi
0.3	Draft	26/04/2023	Authors: Gyula Gábor Tóth (GD); Zsuzsanna Király (GD); Mária Csikai (GD)
0.4	Draft	27/04/2023	Reviewers: Torsten Wähler (MLU); Agnes Zolyomi
1.0	Final	30/04/2023	Reviewer: Torsten Wähler (MLU)

Contributors to action/intervention directly leading to this deliverable

Alex Franklin (CU); Sebastien Kaye; Ilkhom Soliev (MLU); Torsten Wähler (MLU); Agnes Zolyomi

Recommended citation

Tóth, G. G., Király, Z., & Csikai, M. (2023). Communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy (version 1.0). Report No D5.1 of the Horizon Europe Project 101082212 – PLANET4B. Brussels: European Research Executive Agency. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15479762

Rights and license

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The Creative Commons Attribution license allows re-distribution and re-use of a licensed work on the condition that the creator is appropriately credited. [Read more](#).

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Definition
CDE	Communication Dissemination and Exploitation
CG	CzechGlobe – Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences
CGE	Culture Goes Europe
COMCOM	Communication Committee
CU	Coventry University
D	Deliverable
DC	DADIMA'S C.I.C.
EO	Expected Outcome
ESSRG	Environmental Social Science Research Group
FiBL	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture
FUG	Forum Urban Gardening
GA	Grant Agreement – Project 101082212 – PLANET4B
GD	Good Issue Ltd.
IFZ	Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture
IPBES	Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MLU	Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg
M	Month (of the project time)
NINA	Norwegian Institute for Nature Research
OOF	Greater Oslo Council for Outdoor Recreation
PCT	Project Coordination Team
PLANET4B	understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social IEarning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making
PP	Project Partner
UNEP-WCMC	United Nations Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre
UNIFI	University of Pisa
WP	Work Package

Table of Content

Key deliverable information	iii
List of abbreviations and acronyms	v
1 Executive Summary	3
2 About the PLANET4B project	3
3 The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy	3
3.1 Introduction	3
3.2 Defining Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation	4
3.3 Objectives	5
3.4 Strategy and Planning	5
4 Target Audience and Messages	6
4.1 General Messages of the Project	6
4.2 Policymakers	8
4.3 Businesses	9
4.4 Civil Society	11
4.5 Scientific Community, Researchers	13
4.6 Youth, Educators and Social Movements	14
4.7 Local Communities	15
4.8 General Public	15
5 Communication and Dissemination plan	16
5.1 Timeline of the First Year	16
5.2 Project Partner's Responsibilities and Workflow	21
6 Communication Channels and Tools	22
6.1 Visual Identity	22
6.2 Written Contents	23
6.3 Website	23
6.4 Social Media Channels	24
6.5 Newsletter	27
6.6 Briefs	28
6.7 Press Releases	28
6.8 Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications	28
6.9 Emails	29
6.10 Open-Source Platforms	29
6.11 Events	29
6.12 Consultations	29

6.13 Other Visual Tools.....	30
6.14 Media Relations	30
7 Synergies	30
8 Internal Communication	31
8.1. Internal Communication Rules and Tools	32
9 Exploitation.....	32
10 Monitoring Results.....	34

1 Executive Summary

This document is the Deliverable D5.1 – “Communication, dissemination and exploitation (CDE) strategy” of Work Package 5 (Capacity building, cooperation, communication, and upscaling to accelerate change) in the PLANET4B project.

This CDE strategy will provide an overview of PLANET4B’s:

- communication and dissemination objectives;
- main messages;
- target groups;
- and the main CDE relevant activities.

It will also detail the tasks and responsibilities of PPs as well as the first year’s plan of concrete actions. The implementation and indicators of the CDE will be regularly monitored updated and will be revised in M18 and M35.

2 About the PLANET4B project

We rely on biodiversity for our very existence – it provides us with the basic ecosystem services that allow us to survive and thrive. Still, human lives and the biosphere itself are under threat due to the loss of biodiversity occurring at a massive scale, and at an accelerating pace. Despite the mounting scientific evidence on the importance of biodiversity, it still takes a back seat to political and other agendas.

How can we change this alarming situation? The PLANET4B (understanding Plural values, intersectionality, Leverage points, Attitudes, Norms, behaviour and social IEarning in Transformation for Biodiversity decision making) research project aims to understand and influence decision making affecting biodiversity. The project’s main objectives are: 1) to understand how factors such as gender, religion, ethnicity, race, age, culture, disability, norms, values and behaviour intersect and are implicated in biodiversity relevant decision making across a range of different scales and settings; and 2) to channel this understanding of complexity into the design of stakeholder interventions, transformative pathways and a series of targeted, yet scalable policy recommendations in order to prioritise biodiversity and halt biodiversity loss.

3 The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy

3.1 Introduction

There are two major communication challenges the project faces. Probably the most significant one is that the communication sphere is overcrowded. The project’s target audience are constantly overwhelmed with information. The other challenge is that PLANET4B is a (technical) research project but one of its main aims is to influence decision makers (to generate transformative change), which are often hard to reach. Both challenges can be addressed in several ways in order to have more significant impact, or more engagement with decision makers.

To stand out and optimise the impact of PLANET4B – with the help of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy – the project will develop clear, understandable, targeted and co-created messages to the target groups, while also presenting key results in both structurally and visually engaging ways. The main objective of the communication activities is to increase the visibility of the project and its results ensuring that the scientific work is effectively communicated. The communication activities will go beyond reaching and engaging with the key target groups (policy-makers, businesses, civil society, scientific community, youth and educators), and will also focus on local communities and stakeholders of the project’s case studies, and on the general public.

Central to the communication activities is content creation, which will be built on the close cooperation among the PPs. These contents will be related to e.g. how we perceive biodiversity, what research results are there on how we make relevant decision making or how local stakeholders can build transformative pathways. As one of the central aspects of the project is to understand how intersectional characteristics define decision making, careful consideration of different cultural and social contexts will be made during the project’s communication and dissemination activities.

3.2 Defining Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Using the EU’s definition¹ (in relation to Horizon Europe projects): communication is “reaching out to society and showing the impact and benefits of EU-funded activities.”, whereas communication activities, within the frame of EU projects are to “inform about and promote the project and its results, success in a non-technical manner.” Dissemination, on the other hand, focuses on the public disclosure of results, enabling others (policy makers, researchers, etc.) to use or re-use or internalise results and thus maximise the impact of EU-funded research.

However, communication and dissemination activities are intertwined and therefore cannot always be clearly distinguished from each other. “The boundaries between certain activities – in particular with regard to communication actions and dissemination – are often blurry or can sometimes overlap. For instance, a magazine article highlighting the project’s work and achievements that is written for communication purposes could end up in the hands of potential stakeholders outside the project and trigger interest in using some of the results. The initial communication activity has now become a dissemination tool as well.”²

¹ For all citations in this chapter see European IT Helpdesk (2022) as the relevant reference: European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Scherer, J., Weber, S., Alveen, P., et al. (2022). European IP Helpdesk. Successful valorisation of knowledge and research results in Horizon Europe. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation. Ingbert: Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/437645> (accessed April 24, 2023).

² For all citations in this chapter see European IT Helpdesk (2022) as the relevant reference: European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Scherer, J., Weber, S., Alveen, P., et al. (2022). European IP Helpdesk. Successful valorisation of knowledge and research results in Horizon Europe. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation. Ingbert: Publications Office of the European Union. Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/437645> (accessed April 24, 2023).

Exploitation is the utilisation and commercialisation of the results and outcomes of the research project. This includes finding ways to bring the knowledge generated by the project ensuring that the results are used effectively to create economic, social, and environmental benefits. It is the effective use or re-use of the project's results in scientific, economic, political or social ways with the aim of translating the project's actions into tangible value creating economic, social, and environmental benefits. This includes finding ways to bring the knowledge generated by the project to the market.

3.3 Objectives

The main purpose of this document is to provide a clear definition and explanation of the various communication instruments as well as the target audience and strategies in formulating messages. This will help PPs communicate more effectively and ensure that their efforts are aligned with achieving the project goals. Additionally, the CDE strategy and the annual CDE plan clearly outline the roles and responsibilities of each partner in executing different communication and dissemination activities. By establishing clear accountability, the plan aims to optimise communication efforts and maximise their impact on the intended audience. The CDE strategy and plan will also ensure that relevant actions address the key target groups with tailored messages through the relevant channels and in the most appropriate formats.

The overarching goal of the communication and dissemination activities is to initiate, accelerate and upscale biodiversity-relevant transformative changes in our society by disseminating the project results to researchers, scientific and policy-making institutions and networks, the related target groups and the general public. In addition, these activities aim to increase the visibility of the project and its results, ensuring that the scientific work is effectively communicated (and to understand how to communicate biodiversity more effectively). The activities defined in the plan are designed to raise awareness and maximise the impact of the project outputs.

Based on the experience of the project's first year, the CDE strategy will be updated in M18 and M35. The strategy will be monitored and updated regularly (every 6 month), and based on it, the CDE plan will be created annually with consultation of the PPs.

3.4 Strategy and Planning

This CDE strategy is designed to help the PPs communicate effectively to achieve the project's objectives. This document defines the strategy's objectives (why we want to do it), the target audience (for whom), the messages (what we want to say), the channels (how we want to say it) and the actions (what we want to do). In other words: the CDE strategy aims to identify who needs to be reached and in what way, and when the target groups need to be addressed in order to successfully achieve a more substantial impact.

To achieve this, WP5 leader Good Issue (GD) will provide annual internal planning (see Table 9: Communication and Dissemination plan for Year 1) to share the communication and dissemination related tasks among PPs. This communication and dissemination strategy works as a detailed roadmap to organise the communication work according to timeline, needs and resources. While the strategy focuses on "what to do", the plan instructs "how to do it" providing guidance on how to implement the

strategy. The plan is specific, time-based and developed regularly, while the strategy is updated in M18 and M35 and submitted as separate deliverables.

4 Target Audience and Messages

4.1 General Messages of the Project

In respect of interacting with the target audience and motivating it to act, clearly defined messages are crucial. Messages articulate and encapsulate what the project is about, but more importantly why it is vital and relevant for the target groups. Messages should convey responses to: Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we offer to them? What do we want them to do?

Relevant messages can (and should) be used in every project activity, whether a partner is posting on social media, presenting at a conference, writing the summary of a report or talking to a journalist. Messages can help partners to improve communication, to influence decision making and to achieve impact.

The following table (Table 1) includes examples for general messages, relating to the topics of the project, to aspects of credibility (e.g. to gain trust) as well as to aspects of novelty of the project’s work.

Table 1. Main general messages of the project.

Category	Message
Topic-related (biodiversity, decision making, etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss threatens our existence. Yet, this crisis is only getting worse showing inapt governance. • Our current socio-economic system building on consumption and overexploitation stands against nature and biodiversity (and us). • To affectively address this system and trigger transformation, we need to better understand why biodiversity is not prioritised at the first place. • Within PLANET4B, we will look into why we do not already prioritise biodiversity and nature although we all find it important. • We will assess governing norms, values and belief systems as well as intersectionality aspects (e.g. gender, age, race, religion). • We will use transdisciplinary research and practices from economy through conservation to arts to analyse how we can make biodiversity more of a priority at individual, community and institutional level. • We will provide practical guidance for policy-makers, civil society members and businesses about how they can change minds and make better decisions for biodiversity saving the planet. • We will assess how religion, age, gender, disability and race may influence decision making on prioritising biodiversity through 11 case studies from eight countries. • We will assess how various sectors (education, fashion industry, finance, agriculture, trade) can reduce

	<p>individual and institutional barriers to upscale biodiversity decision making.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • We will attempt to understand how the locally gained knowledge can be built into the global level influencing major policies. • We will bridge a knowledge gap about understanding how biodiversity can be prioritised in individual and policy decision making. • The PLANET4B project deals with the globally relevant topic of biodiversity loss that affects all humankind and has consequences for our future and survival (keywords: our existence, crucial, survival, alarming, biodiversity loss, etc.). • The project tries to understand how we can make decision making prioritise biodiversity more. • The project supports transformative actions for biodiversity.
Credibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The PLANET4B project is a cooperation between 16 partners from 10 countries: renowned universities, NGOs and SMEs, from all around Europe. • More than 60 researchers and experts are working on the outcomes.
Novelty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PLANET4B performs unique research on the topic. • Thanks to the consortium's wide transdisciplinary composition, the project can integrate knowledge from different disciplines (including political sciences, economics, sociology, psychology and communication sciences) as well as build on policy and practical knowledge. • The project compiles a much-needed gap-filling knowledge resource. • The project's research process is transdisciplinary, creative, action-oriented and participatory. • The findings will be synthesised and scaled up to EU and global levels. • The project hopes to trigger transformative change so biodiversity can be prioritised in decision making.

The target groups of the project are:

- Policymakers
- Businesses
- Civil society
- Scientific community
- Local communities
- Youth, educators and social movements
- General public

Before dissemination activities can be realised, certain questions need to be clarified in order to better understand and address the specific target group: What do we know about them? (What are their needs, news/information consuming habits?) What do we want to say/offer to them? How can we help them? What do we want them to do? What is their role in the solution?

4.2 Policymakers

One of the most influential actors to trigger transformative change may be relevant policy-makers. In order to prioritise biodiversity and halt biodiversity loss, the co-produced knowledge of the project will be channelled into targeted, yet scalable policy recommendations. The project participants will ensure that the co-produced knowledge reaches the policymakers at the public and private levels, and that relevant knowledge is considered in policy-making. As a result of the dissemination, policymakers will understand better the importance of biodiversity, their role in transformation changes, the integration option of biodiversity to policy, the various factors defining decision making and the relevant institutional barriers and enablers. They will be able to make more effective biodiversity policy implementation, better policy formulation and prioritisation of biodiversity as well as better consideration of biodiversity in implementation. In addition, they will not only have a better understanding of the reviews and evaluation of policies but also integrate biodiversity into sectoral policy transitions. Furthermore, the dissemination of results will ensure policy coherence with international processes and aid plausible policy transitions.

The policymakers will be reached mainly through bilateral policy consultations and policy events as well as via the project’s social media channels, using news, posts, briefs, illustrated transitional stories and policy reports. There will be three workshops with EU policymakers (e.g. DG ENG, DG AGRI, DG CLIMA). These workshops and consultations will take place in-person in Brussels or at relevant international events organised by the PPs with a maximum of 20 representatives/participants from the target groups per workshop. The workshops will build on (and integrate the results of) the specific case studies from WP3. Sectoral specific policy recommendations (agriculture, trade, finance, industry, education) about how transition can be upscaled to the EU and global levels will be communicated through 10 consultations with key enablers. Collaborating with relevant UN bodies (e.g. UNEP, UNDP, UN Women) will further ensure relevant messages are received by target groups and policy processes.

The recommendations for EU and international policies (about how behavioural and intersectionality insights can aid policy coherence and implementation and how biodiversity can be further prioritised) will reach 100 enabling players using a synthesis policy report.

The following table (Table 2) includes specific messages for policymakers, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 2. Specific messages for policymakers.

<p>Messages for policy makers: What do we offer them? Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we want them to do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the PLANET4B outcomes policymakers can communicate better about biodiversity issues. • Policymakers can make more effective policy formulation and implementation in relation to biodiversity. • Policymakers can integrate biodiversity consideration in policy-making. • The project results provide a deeper understanding of the motivation behind business, institutional and private decision making that helps to implement existing biodiversity related policies more effectively.
---	--

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project can aid understanding how policies can best have a positive impact on biodiversity. • The project reveals major causes of limited biodiversity prioritisation and provide enablers for transformative change to limit and ultimately, stop biodiversity change. • The project promotes biodiversity and nature-based solutions that contribute to the food, water and raw materials security. • Policymakers can find the field of cooperation with businesses, education, scientific sector and civil society working on biodiversity topics from local to global levels.
Relevant outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D4.1 – Entry points for upscaling findings at relevant scales identified, based on consultations with key enabling players (EU policy makers and businesses). • D4.2 – Mapping of leverage points and transformative pathways for upscaling at the EU as well as global context, produced for five sectors (agriculture, finance, education, industry, trade). • D4.3 – Reports from workshops on validated methods and pathways at EU, global and sector level. • D4.4 – Knowledge products, including synthesis of the applicability of behaviour science and intersectionality for prioritising biodiversity into relevant EU and global processes. • D5.8 – Three comprehensive guidelines tailored for enabling players (civil society, policy-makers and businesses).
Timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuously, during the project • Intensive dissemination: M28–M36
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops • Meetings, bilateral consultations • Social media (LinkedIn, Twitter) • Newsletter • Conferences, events
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy report • Presentations • Briefs • Infographics • Illustrated transformative change stories

4.3 Businesses

Business decisions are crucial in preventing biodiversity loss as companies have a direct impact on the environment through their operations and supply chains. They can also influence consumer behaviour and policies through their actions and advocacy. To stop biodiversity loss, businesses can adopt sustainable sourcing, energy efficiency, corporate responsibility practices that prioritise sustainability and biodiversity, and advocate for policies that support conservation and sustainability. Overall, businesses have the power to positively or negatively impact biodiversity.

To engage financing and business leaders, the project will host a series of stakeholder workshops. Business entities can be reached through other activities, such as social media and presentations. These activities will build on (and integrate the results of) the specific case studies from WP3 (especially the case studies working with finance, and with local businesses).

Examples of businesses, with which the consortium has established links, include: Proteus Partnership, TNFD partners, Natural Capital organisations, World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD), Green Economy Coalition, EU Business@Biodiversity Platform.

The following table (Table 3) includes specific messages for businesses, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 3. Specific messages for businesses.

<p>Messages for policy makers: What do we offer them? Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we want them to do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss is mainly triggered by the dominant global economic system – hence we need businesses to contribute to transformative changes. • Businesses contribute to biodiversity loss because of unsustainable practices, but with transformative changes and changing their values system, they can contribute to saving biodiversity and the society. • The current consumption practices have long-term destructive and detrimental effects on both nature and human health and well-being. • We need transformative change in the system in order to survive. • Making positive decisions for biodiversity businesses can answer the emerging “green” consumer needs better and reach a wider audience (consumers). • “More sustainable” businesses can make a significant impact. • They can manage and sustain their own resources better. • Transformative change can boost resilient production, higher quality of food, water and raw material security; understanding of new market demands; adaptation to climate change, early adaptation to future policies (fashion case study). • They can offer “greener” solutions to their respective market (finance case study). • They can diversify your portfolio.
<p>Relevant outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.8 – Three comprehensive guidelines tailored for enabling players (civil society, policymakers and businesses). • WP3 outcomes, WP4 outcomes
<p>Timeframe</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From M6
<p>Channels</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops and consultations • Social media • Newsletter • Media-news
<p>Tools</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Briefs • Infographics • Illustrated transformative change stories

4.4 Civil Society

Civil society organisations (e.g. NGOs) play a crucial role in shaping the social, political and economic landscape of any society. One of the key reasons for their importance is their ability to reach and influence a broad segment of the population. Civil societies have existing channels, credibility and resources to engage with people from different backgrounds. Moreover, civil societies have further resources to reach a wide segment of society.

The project will provide guidance and support for target groups within the civil society sector in order to not only communicate better about biodiversity issues but also to be a catalysator for influencing policies to have greater societal impacts.

The project aims to reach three different groups that can be categorised under the term civil society:

- 1) Conservation NGOs working at EU and international levels (e.g. members of the European Habitats Forum including WWF, BirdLife, IUCN, Friends of the Earth, European Environmental Bureau, ClientEarth, OCEANA, FERN, Justice and Environment, Indigenous and Community Conserved Areas (ICCA), RARE, GreenPeace, etc.
- 2) Social NGOs working on the local level with communities (consortium partners and their relevant networks – focusing on social issues such as gender, inclusion, diversity, migration, SDGs, etc.
- 3) Organisations of sectoral groups – e.g. European Landowners Organisations (ELO), Copa Cogeca, International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM), Forestry and Trade Associations.

The following table (Table 4) includes specific messages for target groups within the civil society, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 4. Specific messages for target groups within the civil society.

<p>What do we offer them? Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we want them to do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the project’s outcomes (and the knowledge generated in the project about biodiversity, nature-based solutions and ecosystem services) the organisations can communicate and influence decisions better about biodiversity towards their own target audience. • The project outcomes can help them to trigger transformative change. • Their biodiversity relevant communication can be stronger, sharper and more impactful. • They can improve their cooperation and engagement with their stakeholders. • They can plan and organise more impactful campaigns and do advocacy more effectively. • The project offers guidance and training to help their work to reach greater impacts for biodiversity. • They can be empowered with new knowledge of how to communicate relevant information in the best way in order to nudge and drive policy and action to halt biodiversity loss.
<p>Relevant outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.8 – Three comprehensive guidelines tailored for enabling players (civil society, policymakers and businesses). • Trainings • WP3 outcomes, WP4 outcomes
<p>Timeframe</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From M13
<p>Channels</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings • Social media • Newsletter

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Media-news
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training materials • Guidelines • Briefs • Infographics • Illustrated transformative change stories

4.5 Scientific Community, Researchers

The scientific community and researchers can benefit greatly from the results of the PLANET4B project. The results of the project can help to advance scientific knowledge by uncovering new information about biodiversity loss and the factors that contribute to it. It can also help to identify the gaps in our understanding of the topic. This can be conducive to guide future research efforts and ensure that we focus our efforts on the most important areas.

Future research projects can provide policymakers with further information they need to make informed decisions ensuring that policies continue to be based on the most recent scientific results. The project is likely to inspire researchers from different disciplines and backgrounds to collaborate contributing to the formation of interdisciplinary teams and facilitate the exchange of ideas and expertise.

Specific target groups are: representatives of natural science, behavioural science, social science and gender studies focusing on intersectionality, authors of IPBES assessments and IPCC reports, science-policy interfaces (e.g. Eklipse, NetworkNature) researchers in sister projects and other Horizon Europe projects dealing with behavioural theories and transformative change.

The following table (Table 5) includes specific messages for scientific communities, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 5. Specific messages for scientific communities.

<p>What do we offer them? Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we want them to do?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PLANET4B provides specific results and background from the activities to apply transdisciplinary research. • Transdisciplinary research can provide applicable knowledge for decision making relevant to biodiversity. • Transdisciplinary research has the potential to address unanswered questions in conventional scientific fields.
Relevant outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outcomes of WP1 and WP2 • Presentations on conferences, events • Scientific articles
Timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Throughout the project
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social media • Newsletter • Conferences, networking events with similar projects

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific magazines
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications • Presentations • News

4.6 Youth, Educators and Social Movements

To trigger transitions and transformations, the project will increase capacities of youth and education organisations by providing online training resources and guidance. To aid its application among youth groups and movements, a set of educational resources (e.g. creative exercises; interactive games to raise awareness and reflection on biodiversity) will be provided for the secondary and higher curricula as well as other extra-curricular educational settings and organisations (e.g. youth groups, movements, etc.).

Extension of materials and dissemination among schools (along with its adjustment to climate change materials) will be ensured through the consortium partner Climate Academy that directly works with schools throughout the EU. Academic partners and universities will also provide dissemination in higher education on a global scale.

Specific target groups are: school networks of the EU, universities and youth movements – e.g. Fridays for Future, Youth and Environment Europe (YEE), Young Friends of the Earth.

Youth and education organisations will be addressed through the website and social media channels as well.

The following table (Table 6) includes specific messages for the youth and educators, listing their relevant outcomes, timeframe for realisation, channels and tools.

Table 6. Specific messages for the youth and educators.

What do we offer them? Why should they be interested in the project/results? How could they benefit from the results of the project? What do we want them to do?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Using the project outcomes, they can communicate better about biodiversity issues. • They can influence policymakers to make more effective biodiversity policy implementations. • They can raise awareness, promote new attitudes and inspire actions of their target groups.
Relevant outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D5.9 – Online training and educational resources for communicating biodiversity and triggering transformative change. • D5.10 – Adjusted training materials for secondary and higher education.
Timeframe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • M30–M36
Channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trainings • Social media • Newsletter • Conferences • Meetings, bilateral consultations
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online training resources

4.7 Local Communities

Empowered communities can actively contribute to safeguarding biodiversity and implement nature-based solutions. These communities will be reached locally and through organisations like ICLEI (Local Governments for Sustainability), C40 (Cities Climate Leadership Group) or Global Covenant of Mayors.

They will be also reached through the case studies of the project with similar messages to the general public as well as locally relevant messages.

4.8 General Public

Biodiversity loss affects every aspect of our lives including our health, economy and overall well-being – communicating about the project and its results cannot only increase the visibility of the project and help to disseminate its results but also raise awareness of the topic of biodiversity.

Communicating about biodiversity loss (and the importance of our decisions) to a general public is needed to sensitise the issue. This can inspire individuals and communities to take action to protect and conserve biodiversity. By educating people about the importance of biodiversity, they can be encouraged to make lifestyle changes that reduce their impact on the environment, support conservation efforts and advocate for policies that protect biodiversity.

In addition, communicating about biodiversity loss can help bridge the gap between scientists and the public. Scientific research on biodiversity loss can be complex and technical, making it difficult for non-experts to understand. By translating scientific findings into accessible language and presenting them in engaging ways, people can learn about the importance of biodiversity and the urgency of protecting it.

The general public will be informed through the project news (website and newsletter) and social media activities.

Since one of the project's main questions is how biodiversity is currently perceived the project's findings can be used to enhance its own communication activities (EO 1 – information on relevant messages of biodiversity communication³).

The following table (Table 7) includes messages for the general public which can be fine-tuned based on the project's findings. Questions to be asked in this fine-tuning process are: why should the general public care about the project? Why is it interesting/valuable for people? What aspect of the project can be interesting for them? (see also CBD, Global Biodiversity Outlook 5⁴ and WWF, Understanding Biodiversity Awareness in 9 countries⁵).

³ REA (2022). Grant Agreement. Project 101082212 – PLANET4B. Part B, p.5.

⁴ CBD (2020). Global Biodiversity Outlook 5. Available at: <https://www.cbd.int/gbo5> (accessed April 24, 2023).

⁵ WWF (2022). Understanding Biodiversity Awareness in 9 countries. Available at: https://wwfint.awsassets.panda.org/downloads/wwf_global_biodiversity_awareness_study_2022_only_numbers.pdf (accessed April 24, 2023).

Table 7. Messages and examples for general public.

Messages About	Examples
(The importance of) biodiversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We rely on biodiversity for our very existence. It provides us with the basic ecosystem services that allow us to survive and thrive.
Biodiversity loss, scale of the problem, consequences, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alarming and continued loss of biodiversity now threatens both the biosphere and human life because of inapt governance. Over-consumption is an important driver in biodiversity loss.
The importance of decisions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> We make decisions almost every day that can affect biodiversity. We can also influence biodiversity related decisions.
The project – how it works, what solutions we plan to provide	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> See section 3.1 General messages of the project.

5 Communication and Dissemination plan

5.1 Timeline of the First Year

All PPs are actively involved in communication and dissemination activities to achieve the expected impact of the project. By utilising the potentials of the planned channels (e.g. website, social media, newsletter, media contacts, participation in different events) and networks of the PPs, the project has the potential to multiply the effects of disseminating the project results which requires the active participation of the PPs. The distribution of communication and dissemination tasks is based on the project outputs and milestones and the agreement by the PPs (Table 8). Ensuring the highest level of credibility and competence, the communication tasks are aligned with the strengths and capacities of the partner in charge.

Table 9 (Communication and Dissemination plan for Year 1) shows the annual internal planning.

Table 8. Overview of main communication and dissemination activities.

Phase	Main focus, activities, objective
Initial phase, M1–M6	<p>The first phase is about kick-starting the communication and dissemination activities. The main goal is to create a solid base for the upcoming activities (visual identity, designing the website, setting up internal communication). By the end of this phase:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Visual identity (logo, branding, templates, etc.) is ready and shared with the PPs. Website is fully operational (contents are uploaded, there is at least one news article). Social media activities have started (few “warm-up” contents). Some project meetings and presentations are organised.

Operational phase, from M6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broader communication activities will start once the website is fully operational and at least one main/key deliverable is available on it. • Social media activities will be intensified, news on the project website will be published (and further disseminated via the newsletter) and meetings and workshops with key actors will be held during this period. In addition, press releases will be sent to inform the global/regional media about the project.
Maturity phase, close to the end of the project (M30–M36)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Here, the main focus is on the promotion of the concrete results, the final findings/outputs.
Additional phase, after the end of the project	Making sure that the outcomes are available after the project ends (activities for five years after the end of the project).

Table 9. Communication and Dissemination plan for Year 1.

Communication/Dissemination output	Tool	Action	Partner in charge	Target group	Related deliverable	Month of delivery
Report on biodiversity and related concepts perceptions	Public report/article, brief	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. News is included in the newsletter.	FiBL GD	T4	D1.1	M6–M8
Inventory of behaviour science theories potentially influencing biodiversity decision making	Public report, brief	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. News is included in the newsletter.	NINA GD	T4	D1.2.	M6–M8
Methodological framework for intersectionality analysis	Public report, brief	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. News is included in the newsletter.	IFZ GD	T4	D1.3.	M6–M8
Workshop report on key theories of behaviour, decision making and change	Workshop, public report	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. News is included in the newsletter.	RU GD	T5, T1, T2, T3, T4	D1.4.	M6–M8

Workshop report on theory commonalities and conflict	Workshop, public report, article	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. News is included in the newsletter.	RU GD	T5, T1, T2, T3, T4	D1.5.	M12–M14
Directory of key methods most suitable for biodiversity decision making contexts	Public report, brief, article	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. PPs promote report and articles on their channels (social media, website, network). News is included in the newsletter. Article Infographic TV and radio interviews	CU GD	T4, T1, T2, T3	D2.1	M6–M8
Learning communities and sectoral advisory boards established for case studies	Public report, brief, two articles	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (LinkedIn, Twitter) with short explanations. Article1 Article2 PPs promote report and articles on their channels (social media, website, network). News is included in the newsletter.	RU, ESSRG GD	All target groups	D3.1	M9–M11, M12–M14
Project website	Project website	Project website and newsletter are promoted in the social media of the	GD, All PPs	All target groups	D5.4	M3–M5, M6–M8

		project as well as in the social media of the PPs.				
Social media activity	Posts	Relevant social media posts are reshared by the PPs.	GD All PPs	All target groups	D5.1	from M3
Newsletter	Newsletter	Promoted on the website, in the social media and via email. PPs promote the newsletter in their channels (social media, website, network).	GD All PPs	T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6	D5.1	M7–M9
Press release	Press release	Promoted on the website, in the social media and media. PPs contribute to promote their own media contacts.	GD All PPs	All target groups	D5.1	M7–M9
Preliminary synergies strategy	Public report, brief	Report (as well as a brief of the report) is shared on the website. News about the report is posted on the website. Posts are shared in the social media of the project and the PPs (Linkedin, Twitter) with short explanations. News included in the newsletter.	UNEP-WCMC	T4	D5.5.	M6–M9

T1: policymakers, T2: businesses, T3: civil society: (a) conservation NGOs, (b) social NGOs, T4: scientific community, T5: local communities, T6: youth, educators and social movements

5.2 Project Partner's Responsibilities and Workflow

The Communication and Dissemination WP Leader (GD), the contributing PPs and the project coordination team (PCT including MLU, CU, UNEP-WCMC) will work together for effective communication dissemination and exploitation of project results and outcomes.

Tasks and responsibilities of WP5 leader Good Issue (GD):

- Being responsible for the coordination and monitoring processes of Task 5.1 and Task 5.2.
- Creating and regularly revising the Communication Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy that is in line with the EU guidance,⁶ compiling the updated deliverable in M18 and M35.
- Coordinating the communication and dissemination activities among the PPs.
- Based on the CDE strategy, creating an annual work plan of communication and dissemination tasks, closely linked to the defined outcomes, goals and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).
- Co-planning and monitoring PPs' communication and dissemination activities.
- Supporting and supervising of PPs' CDE related tasks.
- Managing the website and social media channels to ensure structured visibility of the outcomes.
- Providing templates and guidelines for the public communication and dissemination as well as visual identity and branding elements.
- Supporting the project outcomes through the promotion of materials and communication tools.
- Contributing to the reporting system using WP5 related outcomes.
- Organisation of bi-monthly meetings of the Communication Committee (COMCOM) with PPs to discuss all tasks, responsibilities and challenges related to communication and dissemination. The main means of internal communication between COMCOM members is email.

Responsibilities and tasks of the project coordination team (MLU, UNEP-WCMC, CU) related to CDE activities:

- Keeping the WP5 lead (GD) informed about the progress of the project and the main outcomes of the discussions related to communication and dissemination activities with the Advisory Board and the European Research Executive Agency (REA) to ensure the proper update of the CDE strategy and plan and daily activities. The main communication tool used for communications will be email and three-monthly bilateral meetings.
- Approving and reviewing the project communication deliverables and outputs.
- Participating in COMCOM meetings and updating internal project management work plan (Miro board) according to the information provided by the PPs.

⁶ European Commission (2020). H2020 Online Manual. Communicating Your Project. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm (accessed April 25, 2023).

Responsibilities and tasks of all PPs related to CDE activities

Implementing effective, competent and reliable communication and dissemination activities – all PPs are involved in the CDE activities and contribute to reach the project level of KPIs undertaken in the Grant Agreement:

- Delegating one person per organisation to the COMCOM. The delegate takes part in the COMCOM meetings and follows the work of the COMCOM.
- Giving inputs to the communication management team (deliverables, reports, articles, photos, events, etc.) on their related activities.
- Adhering to the compulsory visibility elements according to the Grant Agreement Article 17 and the visual identity guideline provided by GD.
- Providing communication and dissemination content according to the annual CDE plan.
- Utilising their existing communication channels on local, national and transnational level (website, social media, newsletter, conferences, events, media lists, etc.) and networks (stakeholders, target groups) to promote PLANET4B's outcomes by sharing the results of the project.
- Reporting on their CDE activities regularly (every six months) following the reporting templates developed by the PCT and GD together.

6 Communication Channels and Tools

6.1 Visual Identity

The visual identity and its practical application (templates) play a critical role in communicating/disseminating the project and its results in a coherent and outstanding way. The visual identity builds on the logo and its elements (shape and colour). The appearance of the logo is simple, but strong, easy to recognise and easy to use. It refers to the name "planet" (concentric circles), biodiversity as our main topic (colours), and also evokes "action" (influence, decision, triggering change, etc. – "target" structure).

In the project's visual communication, we use the following elements: fonts, colour palette, logo, logo variations, logo elements (circular pattern), presentation, deliverable and social media post templates, photos as well as rollup.

Since it is difficult to illustrate the project's complex and abstract concepts (such as "decision making", "biodiversity related decisions", "transformative change", "biodiversity related values, behaviours and norms", etc.) in the visual communication (website, social media posts, etc.) we will use simple, general but strong pictures to accompany the project communication. These pictures are either showing:

- a) positive biodiversity examples (natural forests, green scenery, animals, conservation pictures, etc.) or
- b) images about biodiversity loss.

We will avoid using staged⁷ and symbolic pictures (e.g. globe, etc. in a human hand). When using pictures with people⁸ we intend to choose an illustration that is as authentic as possible.

The visual identity is explained in the Brand Guideline, which will be shared with the consortium. PPs will use the visual elements through their social media posts, presentation and report (deliverable) templates.

Visibility and Use of Funders' Logos

PLANET4B receives EU and non-EU funds – UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) and State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) from Switzerland – for the project implementation. Pursuant to the legal agreements with the funder organisations, in any public communication and dissemination activities of the PPs, the logos and acknowledgement of funding must be indicated (see project Brand Guideline). The relevant rules are laid down in the Grant Agreement (Art. 17) and in separate agreements with UKRI and SERI.

6.2 Written Contents

Addressing the communication challenge, we face (e.g. an overcrowded communication sphere), we will apply a set of rules to our written communication that are consistent with the EU communication guidelines and the latest trends in science communication. When communicating about the results of the project, it is important to use a language, a style, and an approach that is clear, concise and accessible to a wide range of an audience.

Wherever possible, in our communication we will use a clear and simple language and messages that avoid using jargon or technical terms that may be unfamiliar to non-experts. Where necessary, we will define any technical terms. We will try to avoid overly technical or complex explanations and instead focus on the description of our findings in a way that is easy to understand. By doing so, we can help to ensure that the research results are understood and valued by a diverse audience, contributing to the goal of creating a greater societal impact.

6.3 Website

The PLANET4B website (<https://planet4b.eu/>) will be the main interface for communication with the public and will be updated regularly. The website traffic will be monitored using Google Analytics which provides data on users and their interactions with the website.

Beyond the main function of introducing the project and the participants the website will:

⁷ A staged photograph, also known as a stock photograph, is an image that is taken with the purpose of being licensed and used in various media, such as advertisements, websites, and magazines. Photos of this kind are usually shot in a controlled environment, with models or objects carefully arranged and posed to convey a particular message or idea.

⁸ The use of photographs picturing people will always follow the principles of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of PLANET4B: it requires ethical considerations, including obtaining consent, respecting privacy, avoiding misrepresentation, respecting ownership and avoiding exploitation.

- make the results (deliverables) easily available for download and use through a clear and accessible structure;
- share news, articles, events;
- attract audience for the newsletter;
- build up trust by transparency (sharing information about the project, the participants, etc.).

The website will be operated by GD under the supervision of the PCT.

The website structure is as follows.

Main/opening (home) page

The opening page is technically a quick snapshot of the project using short information bits in a scroll-down structure. Its elements are: banner slide (3–4 moving banners; one will show a project slogan another will promote a report or an event), project description (short description with a “read more” option), latest news (2–3 of the latest or most important news), partners (logos of the PPs), “sign up for newsletter” panel, “ask the expert” panel, contact, social media icons (LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube), disclaimer/privacy policy, etc.

About

The project: a short description of the goal(s) of the project and its main activities. Partners: introduction of the PPs with a short description of the respective organisation and its the role in the project. Team members: name, photo, link to LinkedIn profile.

Case studies

Collection of 11 stories (case studies). Each case study on this page will have a sub-page with the accompanying information (plus photos, videos, etc.).

Library

Project documents: all of the deliverables and outputs (reports, articles, etc.) will be uploaded for download. The website uses tags choosing between the type (report/article/brief/policy, paper/training material, etc.) as well as the topic/category of the document (communication/decision, making/transformational change, etc.) Media: newsletters, press releases, logo book.

News

News: news about the projects, its outcomes, similar projects, etc. and other related contents (interviews, blog entries, etc.). Events: participation in public events (conferences, workshops, etc.) related to the PLANET4B project; contributions of PPs (e.g. presentation, panel discussion, poster, etc.) will be promoted on the website.

Number of website visitors planned: 5.000.

6.4 Social Media Channels

PLANET4B aims to have a strong presence in social media, enhancing the outreach to its target audience and the broader public. To ensure the maximum of usability and exploitation and to make the best use of the already developed social media networks of the PPs the focus has been given to those social media that PPs have been using

regularly and successfully to communicate and interact with their partners and other stakeholders.

Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram and YouTube (Table 10) have been selected as the most appropriate social networks to promote the project achievements, news and outcomes. Regarding the communication about the project and the dissemination of its results we will primarily use the project's own social media channels. While LinkedIn and Twitter are to be used to reach specific target groups, Instagram will serve as a tool to address the general public. The project's YouTube channel will function as a platform to have access to the project's video contents (e.g. videoclips from workshops).

To ensure that all relevant target groups are regularly addressed, the responsibility also lies with the PPs to make frequent use of their institutes' channels – website, newsletter and social media (Table 10). In addition, we will build on the potentials of other projects under the Horizon Europe calls. Together with the PPs, GD will reach out to communication teams of other projects or organisations as part of Task 5.3 of WP5 in order to involve them in the planned communication activities.

Fitting into their own social media routine, PPs (as well as individuals) are also encouraged to develop their own contents – not just to repost PLANET4B news and contents but to post information on events they attended, workshops they organised or any other content relating to PLANET4B topics. Since these posts are designed to address individuals to be using a more personal tone, they can mobilise a different level of potential in the communication and dissemination activities.

PLANET4B social media links:

- <https://www.linkedin.com/in/planet4b-project/>
- <https://twitter.com/Planet4bProject>
- <https://www.instagram.com/planet4b/>
- <https://www.youtube.com/@horizoneuropeplanet4b>

Official hashtag: #PLANET4B

Other recommended hashtags: #biodiversity, #transformativechange #policy #governance #pluralvalues #intersectionality #time4betterdecisions #behaviourchange

Number of social media followers planned: 1.000.

Number of social media posts planned: 700.

Table 10. PLANET4B relevant platforms and contents.

Platform	Content
Social media of PLANET4B (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram)	Sharing different contents (see the post types below)
Social media of PPs (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram)	Sharing the main project news/results by: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reposting the PLANET4B's social media contents • developing their own contents (attending events, etc.)
Social media of PPs' individuals (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram)	Sharing the main project news/results, shorter news about meetings, events, etc. but also personal insights by:

- reposting the PLANET4B's social media contents
- creating their own contents

Table 11. Existing social media channels of the PPs.

PP	LinkedIn	Twitter	Instagram	YouTube	Facebook
MLU	26k	12.2k	17.1k	3.36k	31k
NINA	7k	1258	2380	7.36k	13k
CU	248k	73.6k	49.1k	17.8k	195k
UNEP-WCMC	58k	21.6k	-	-	70k
CGE	0,2 k	170	1.3k	20	3.8k
CAC	-	-	400	-	-
DC	-	-	800	-	2.4k
FUG	-	-	-	-	600
CG	17	750	300	84	2.2k
ESSRG	1k	200	-	175	-
IFZ	67	600	500	-	-
GD	-	-	-	-	250
OOF	6k	48.7k	308k	5.2k	237k
RU	167k	30.8k	27.7k	6.9k	44k
FiBL	14k	5.9k	-	-	7k
UNIFI	135k	19.5k	34.3k	6k	70k

Post types:

- News about deliverables (short summary, keywords, background, importance, link, etc.)
- Promoting short interviews of key persons/partner organisations
- Introducing partner organisations (their role, etc.)
- Upcoming events, conferences
- Upcoming workshops (promotion of workshops)
- Promoting sister project(s)
- News outside of the project
- Promoting the newsletter
- Promoting the “Ask the Expert” option
- Posts on Instagram about successful diversity campaigns and visuals (UN, WWF, Greenpeace, etc.)

The visuals accompanying the posts are produced by GD using project-branded Canva templates. If necessary, the editable visuals will also be shared with the PPs to make their own posts.

Quick social media guideline

Below we provide some guidance for PPs about how to use social media:

- Use a language/tone that fits your audience. You could ask them a question or use a quote or a set of emojis and encourage them to comment under your post and share their experience.
- Use appropriate language and tone when posting on social media. Avoid using overly technical language or jargon.
- Make it clear that you are affiliated with a particular institution or organisation. This can help to establish your credibility and avoid confusion about your role and authority.
- Avoid discussing controversial topics that are unrelated to your research. This can help to avoid potential conflicts and ensure that your social media presence remains professional.
- Use multimedia content: visual communication is a very important aspect of all social media channels. Images, videos, infographics, factoids, quotes, etc. catch the user's attention much faster and effectively than text on its own. This kind of content can easily be used to tell a story and helps to engage the audience emotionally. You can use the PLANET4B social media templates in Canva.
- When posting graphs use a clear title that briefly explains the findings. Keep graphs simple (under about 10 data points). This may mean highlighting just a portion of a graph or data from the report.
- When writing a post on social media try to keep the number of words around 10–20 (posting with photo) and 30–40 words (posting without photo). Word count includes all words (dates, names, sources, etc. – everything).

Consider the platform you are posting on and the norms and expectations of that platform carefully. For example, Twitter has a character limit, while LinkedIn is more focused on professional networking.

For more tips: “Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects”.⁹

6.5 Newsletter

PLANET4B e-Newsletters will be released every six months, offering the project community an overview of the latest project activities and developments. E-Newsletters will be both uploaded on the project website and distributed to a list of recipients. The newsletter aims to enable the subscribers to get first-hand information about the project and other projects related to PLANET4B as well as relevant and important news about our main topics. The first newsletter will be released once the website is launched.

The newsletter will be created through MailChimp, a web-based email marketing service. It will be distributed to a mailing list containing subscriber information gathered through a sign-up form on the website. PPs may also promote the newsletter through their channels. An unsubscribe/opt-out link will be available as per EU directive 2002/58/EC.

⁹ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (2020). H2020 Programme. Guidance Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf (accessed April 25, 2023).

GD will coordinate the editing of the newsletter. A mailing template will be designed for this purpose. The sender will always be the official account of the project, planet4b@zirs.uni-halle.de.

For the promotion of the newsletter, the following channels will be used:

- Social media posts
- Website
- Channels of the PPs' institutes (website, social media channels, newsletters, events, etc.)
- Direct email (when contacting a target group, a line should be added to the email about subscribing to the newsletter)

6.6 Briefs

One-page summaries (creative briefs) will be created of each deliverable enabling results to relevant to enabling players. These short briefs will be based on the deliverable, using its relevant sections (executive summary, key findings, etc.) and any additional information provided by the author(s) of the deliverable. All briefs will also be uploaded on the website.

The briefs will be prepared by the Task Leads and edited by GD.

6.7 Press Releases

To further promote the project and its results, press releases will be created by GD when major project news (such as policy recommendations or substantial project results are to be communicated to a wider audience). A press release will be prepared and shared with major European news organisations such as EurActiv, Politico, Policy Review, Reuters and other pan-European news agencies (other examples: ESG Today, Sustain Europe).

Depending on the relevance, PPs will also translate and share information with their own national, regional or local media contacts (both specialised and professional contacts). All press releases will be uploaded on the website as well.

Existing media contacts of the PPs are collected on SharePoint – these contacts will be used to spread the project news.

Number of planned press releases sent: 5.

6.8 Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Scientific publications represent an important means of project result dissemination. We expect that five scientific papers will be published, targeting academics, researchers and relevant professionals. Non-scientific publications have the potential to reach a wider, general and professional audience.

Scientific publications will be written (and sent/uploaded to the scientific sites/magazines) by the PPs, non-scientific publications will be written by the PPs, edited and shared by GD.

Interviews (opinions) of experts within the partner organisations will also be created, attracting media attention on the specific topics.

Guidelines (know-how) on:

- Scientific articles:
<https://www.european-science.org/how-to-write-a-scientific-article/>
- Popular science articles:
<https://royalsociety.org/blog/2017/08/writing-popular-science-as-a-scientist/>

Number of scientific articles planned: 5

Number of non-scientific articles planned: 30

6.9 Emails

One of the primary means of stakeholder outreach in PLANET4B will be one-on-one email to inform interested parties about project results, events and activities. We will also use emails to distribute our newsletter to stakeholders drawing attention to the project's highlights. Emails will allow PPs to conduct a small scale targeted outreach with a more personal rhetoric; however, while email is a simple form of communication, it can be difficult to strategically plan and measure its effectiveness.

6.10 Open-Source Platforms

The project's deliverables and relevant open access data will be also shared on open-source platforms such as OER Commons, OpenSDG, Zenodo and OpenAIRE.

6.11 Events

PPs will disseminate deliverables by participating in national and international scientific conferences as well as international EU policy and business events in order to further promote the project and engage other stakeholders while raising awareness of the PLANET4B activities and expected results. The PPs will represent the consortium and attend debates, lead debates, deliver project-related speeches, contact stakeholders and/or carry out workshops.

PPs should inform the PCT as well as the communication team about their contribution before attending events. After the event, PPs should share the material communicated (e.g. presentation) with any other relevant information so the communication team can create content (news, posts, etc.) about it.

To enable tracking of relevant events including scientific conferences and policy events, (channelling outcomes to accelerate change) a database was created and featured on the internal communication platform on SharePoint as part of Task 5.4 of WP5.

6.12 Consultations

Key enabling players (mostly EU and UN decision makers, business representatives, civil society members, relevant EU and global projects and initiatives) will be contacted and informed about the project and its results through bilateral in-person or electronic

consultations. Additionally, through WP3 and its series of learning communities, local level stakeholders will be regularly consulted.

Stories of transformative change from the case studies' relevant places and sectors and economic value chains will be compiled. Transformation pathways will be produced. These outputs of PLANET4B as well as relevant interventions will be discussed with key enabling players among the target audience in order to enable upscaling at EU and global levels through these consultations.

Number of planned consultations: 10.

6.13 Other Visual Tools

Accompanying the promotion of the different outputs, simple but creative infographics will be created by GD. The PPs are also encouraged to develop infographics (and other similar visuals) using their own resources to aid their reports or social media activities. The production of these visual tools will be coordinated and guided by GD.

Supporting the final results of the project, videoclips will be developed under the supervision of GD. Slightly edited, short (few minutes) versions of the workshop recordings will also be made available on the website.

6.14 Media Relations

Apart from the press releases, PPs will share information about the results of the projects through their own existing media relations in order to generate TV and radio presence in the local/regional media. GD will oversee the coordination of these activities.

7 Synergies

To maximise the project's impact, synergies with other relevant Horizon Europe and non-Horizon projects and initiatives will be mapped, connection and cooperation will be established, and joint work and outputs (e.g. press releases, posts, events) will be initiated under Task 5.3 (Mapping synergies and creating cooperation with existing initiatives and projects) of WP5. The main dissemination tools of the project will be continuously worked on and reflected in line with the target groups and the mapping and synergies seeking activities.

The synergies strategy (D5.5) outlines how collaboration with external projects and initiatives whose areas of work have synergies with PLANET4B will take place. In this strategy, different types of collaborations are defined, types of projects and initiatives to collaborate with are outlined as well as a timeline for collaboration. This includes a seven-step process (identifying, assessing, contacting, coordinating and implementing, communicating, monitoring, setting future collaboration) detailing how to work with external partners based on the identified synergies. Therefore, the primary focus of the synergies strategy is to act as an internal guidance document for PPs. An initial database of over 70 EU and international projects and initiatives that are synergistic with PLANET4B has already been created (see in D5.5) and will be updated on a rolling basis.

8 Internal Communication

The purpose of the internal communication section is to ensure that the external communication tasks are carried out as efficiently as possible by all the consortium members. Furthermore, it aims to make communication and dissemination workflow (tasks, responsibilities, monitoring) transparent.

8.1. Internal Communication Rules and Tools

Planning and Management Tools

The basic tools that will be used during the project to accomplish the planning and carrying out of communication and dissemination activities among the PPs are:

- Communication and Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) strategy and plan: This document contains the main goals, tools and responsibilities on CDE activities of the consortium with key messages, main actors, channels and specific activities, timeline and KPIs. The document is renewed every six months.
- The project management work plan (Miro board): Miro board that contains all the PLANET4B activities, CDE activities and outcomes (deliverables, KPIs, milestones) as a detailed work plan of the consortium.
- COMCOM meeting: The Communication Committee (COMCOM) members meet online bi-monthly to share and discuss CDE related issues, refresh the project management work plan regarding CDE related tasks as well as prepare the renewing of the CDE plan.

Internal Communication Tools

The main tools of internal communication:

- Regular emails
- COMCOM, periodic meetings (online bi-monthly)
- WP Leads meetings (online every four months)
- Steering Committee meetings (annually)

Intranet – SharePoint/Teams

For now, the PLANET4B project's main internal documentation and information sharing platform SharePoint/Teams is provided by CU. SharePoint/Teams is open for all PPs. This private tool will enhance the information exchange among all PPs (minutes, internal documents, WP's specific information, etc.) as well as facilitate internal coordination. The related communication and dissemination documents and plans can be found under the WP5 folder.

9 Exploitation

The European Commission describes exploitation as “the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.”¹⁰

Exploitation is the effective use of project results through scientific, economic, political or societal routes of utilisation. The objective of exploitation is to go one step further than dissemination and turn research and innovation actions into concrete value and impact for society. Thus, the main audience of exploitation is the same with the one suitable for dissemination.

¹⁰ European Commission (2023). EU Grants. AGA – Annotated Grant Agreement. EU Funding Programmes 2021–2027. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf (accessed April 25, 2023).

PLANET4B will aid the exploitation of the results through three fundamental steps:

- 1) Producing a thorough and reflective CDE plan that will continuously be updated to reflect on the exploitation opportunities of the project outcomes. The plan will include exact steps to identify the key exploitable results, their potential platforms and future users, IPR strategy, specific plans for each key exploitable result by the consortium and relevant PPs that will also include potential integration and funding opportunities for the continuation and sustainability of the results.
- 2) Generating a visually appealing, user-friendly, relevant and easily findable resources portfolio devised specifically for each target group. Securing the retained relevance of materials over time, ensuring their attractiveness and easy-to-use structures along with an easily navigable website structure and search option; SEO (Search Engine Optimization) will ensure that the resources will be available even after the project's timeline.
- 3) Ensuring that availability and cross-linking of materials are not only operational through PLANET4B's and the PPs' websites but through the Science Service, KCB, BISE, Oppla, Eklipse platforms, along with websites and social media channels on current and also upcoming Horizon Europe projects under the same and relevant calls as well as other open-access channels (e.g. Open SDG platform). To further support dissemination and exploitation, open access EU services will be explored – Open Research Europe, Horizon Results Platform (HRP), Horizon Results Booster, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and CORDIS.

Intellectual property rights

Within the EU funded R&I-projects, several complementary partners from research, small and large industry come together. Therefore, it is important to set common grounds and learn about each other's expectations, aims and needs early on. Exploitation workshops within COMCOM meetings will help to clearly define the key exploitable results, characterise and prioritise them jointly with the PPs. Exploitable results can be of scientific or commercial relevance and may be either published or protected.

Intellectual property (IP) includes:

- Products of the mind
- Products of research and experimentation
- Products of creativity
- Intellectual property, like physical property, can be a valuable asset.
- Physical property and intellectual property as an asset which can be traded (sold, bought, leased, used as collateral or donated)

Intellectual property rights (IPR)

The law provides legal rights to protect your intellectual property, known as intellectual property rights (IPRs):

- Patents (technical inventions)
- Copyright (software, written works, engineering drawings, semiconductor topologies, etc.)
- Design rights (appearance)

- Database rights (creation and arrangement of data)
- Trademarks (utility models/petty patents, etc.)

10 Monitoring Results

In order to achieve the successful implementation of CDE activities and fulfilment of the relevant objectives and KPIs, a systematic monitoring will be carried out throughout the project implementation. The monitoring will be performed internally on an annual basis and will be officially reported in the relevant deliverables. Regular monitoring will allow the identification of possible risks and deviations from the CDE objectives and performance indicators, and the timely planning of any necessary corrections and actions to address potential implementation problems. Such an approach will improve the overall performance of the relevant activities and enable a more efficient evaluation. An online form has been created for reporting all CDE activities PPs are performing. The form is available on SharePoint/Teams to all PPs. Specific CDE and WP5 relevant templates are created for monitoring purposes and will be sent out to request data on a six-month basis from all PPs. Online presence of PLANET4B will be monitored using specific analytics monitoring software, i.e. Google Analytics as well as relevant social media analytics (number, age, source, distribution, location of the visitors on website, number of posts, followers of the project's social media profiles or views of YouTube videos).

Table 11. Key Performance Indicators.

Tools	KPI	Target
Website	No. of visitors	5.000
Newsletter	No. of subscribers	200
Social media	No. of followers No. of posts	1.000 700
Videos, illustrations and artwork	No. of videos produced No. of target group reached	10 500
Infographics	No. of infographics No. of target group reached	5 500
Press release	No. of press releases sent	5
Non-scientific articles (e.g. The Conversation), radio and TV interviews	No. of articles No. of radio interviews No. of TV interviews, spots No. of people reached	30 5 2 100.000
Scientific publication	No. of publications	5
Workshops for enabling players and stakeholders	No. of workshops organised No. of participants	64 200
Consultations	No. of consultations	10
Joint actions with other EU projects (e.g. joint event, joint communication)	No. of actions	10
Presentations at scientific conferences and events	No. of presentations	5
Public deliverables	No. of deliverables	28

Deliverable briefs (a creative, short version of the main messages)	No. of briefs	25
Online training	No. of online training No. of target group participants No. of education institutes/youth group reached	1 300 100